

Quality and risk management

Deliverable D1.3

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

The process of risk identification and management in SCALIBUR will be based upon the principles and guidelines as described by ISO 310001. This report describes the steps of the risk management implementation. This included establishment of the risk management framework and the risk management process including the risk management context, risk identification, analysis, evaluation and treatment. As part of the framework, the responsibilities related to different project roles are described but all parties are encouraged to participate in the risk management process.

Risks related to SCALIBUR can be categorized as technology related risks, organization related risks, market related risks and environment related risks. Risks will be communicated to the project management and handled by the relevant project body: The General Assembly, the Executive Board or the Innovation Committee. Risk treatment will be approved at the appropriate level of management. The risk management report will be subject to continuous review and it will be updated in case of new risk identified or modifications.

In this report, we describe procedures for risk monitoring and treatment. We identify risks in the various categories, the likelihood of occurrence and sketch risk treatment measures.

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